

Part I: The Experience of Place – Survey for Incarcerated Individuals

Personal Living Space						
1	I live in a cell.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No			
2	In my cell I live:	<input type="checkbox"/> Alone	<input type="checkbox"/> with 1 cellmate	<input type="checkbox"/> with 2+ cellmates	<input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
3	I live in a dorm.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No			
Appearance		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
4	My living space is painted a pleasant colour.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	My living space is visually attractive.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	In general, the physical design of this prison is attractive.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Facilities		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
7	The plumbing system in my housing unit is reliable, so the toilet and sink generally work.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8	The electrical system in this housing unit is reliable, so the electricity is generally working.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9	The mechanical system in this housing unit is reliable, so mechanical doors, for example, generally work.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lighting (Natural & Artificial)		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
10	My living space receives natural light. (Ex: Sunlight enters my space through a window)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
11	The artificial lighting in my living space is comfortable. (Ex: The lamps give nice lighting)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
12	I have some degree of control over the lighting. (Ex: I can use an On/Off switch)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Noise		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
13	It is too noisy within my housing unit.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
14	The noise makes it difficult to sleep, study, or relax.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Privacy in Personal Space		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
15	My living space is designed so I have some privacy.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
16	I have enough personal space in my living area.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
17	The toilet in my living space is designed to have some degree of privacy (Ex: shower curtain / door)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Temperature		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
18	The temperature in my living space can change. (Ex: When it is hot, the temp can be made cooler)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
19	The temperature in my living space changes appropriately.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
20	I can change the temperature in my living space on my own.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Use of Materials		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
21	The furniture in my living space is comfortable.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
22	'Hard' materials, like concrete and metal, are in my living space.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
23	'Soft' materials, like wood and cork, are in my living space.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
24	The materials in my cell are easy to keep clean.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Ventilation & Fresh Air		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
25	In general, my living space has good air quality.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
26	I sometimes have difficulty breathing because of the air quality in my living space.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Views		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
27	I can see out of a window in my living space.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
28	I can see a view of something other than the prison building outside my window.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

General Prison Spaces

Accessibility		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
29	There are enough ramps or railings for people with disabilities to get around the facility.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
30	I sometimes get lost or disoriented in this facility.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
31	There are enough signs to know where I am when I walk through the prison.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Nature		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
32	I can see nature in this prison. For example, I can see gardens, trees, or wildlife from my window or the yard.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
33	I can touch plants, walk near trees, or work in a garden.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Programming		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
34	There are enough spaces in this facility for <u>rehabilitation</u> programs.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
35	There are enough spaces in this facility for <u>education</u> programs.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
36	There are enough spaces in this facility for <u>religious</u> services.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
37	The design of these spaces is appropriate and helps support the activities within them.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Security Technology		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
38	The technology used in this facility, such as security cameras, helps me feel safe.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
39	The technology used in this facility, such as security cameras, makes me feel like I'm losing privacy.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
40	The amount of technology used in this prison increases my sense of privacy.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Visitation		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
41	The spaces for visitation in this prison feel friendly.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
42	Tables are spaced in a way to allow for private conversations.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
43	There are appropriate spaces or activities provided to help incarcerated individuals interact with their kids.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

44. Improvements

If improvements could be made to your physical environment, what three to five elements would be the **most** important to you to change?

Part I: The Experience of Place – Staff Survey

Resident Living Spaces						
Appearance		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	Living spaces are painted a pleasant colour.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2	In general, living spaces are visually attractive.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3	In general, the physical design of this prison is attractive.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Facilities		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
4	The plumbing system in housing units are reliable, so the toilet and sink generally work.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5	The electrical system in housing units are reliable, so the electricity is generally working.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
6	The mechanical system in housing units is reliable, so mechanical doors, for example, generally work.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Lighting (Natural & Artificial)		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
7	Most living spaces have natural light. (Ex: Sunlight enters my space through a window)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
8	The artificial lighting in living spaces is comfortable. (Ex: The lamps give nice lighting)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
9	Residents have some degree of control over the lighting. (Ex: They can use an On/Off switch)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Noise		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
10	It is too noisy within this housing unit.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
11	The noise I hear in this housing unit makes it difficult to work or focus.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Privacy in Personal Space		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
12	The living space (cell or dorm) is designed so residents have some degree of privacy.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

13	Residents have enough personal space in their cell or dorm.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
14	The toilet areas in living spaces are designed to have some degree of privacy (shower curtain/door)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Temperature		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
15	The temperature in living spaces can change. (Ex: When it is hot, the temp can be made cooler)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
16	The temperature in living spaces changes appropriately.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
17	Residents can change the temperature of their living space on their own.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Use of Materials		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
18	The furniture living spaces seem comfortable.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
19	'Hard' materials, like concrete and metal, are used inside living spaces.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
20	'Soft' materials, like wood and cork, are used inside living spaces.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
21	The materials in living spaces are easy to keep clean.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Ventilation & Fresh Air		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
22	In general, living spaces have good air quality.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
23	I sometimes have difficulty breathing because of the air quality in living spaces.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Views		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
24	Residents can see out of a window in their living space.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
25	Residents can see a view of something other than the prison building outside most windows.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

General Prison Spaces

Staff Break Room						
26	There is a staff break room at this facility.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No			
	<i>If yes,</i>	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
27	The staff break room is comfortable.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
28	I enjoy taking a break in the staff break room.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Accessibility		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
29	There are enough ramps or railings for people with disabilities to get around the facility.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
30	Staff can sometimes get lost or disoriented in this facility.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
31	There are enough signs to know where I am when I walk through the prison.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Nature		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
32	I can see nature in this prison. For example, I can see gardens, trees, or wildlife from windows or the yard.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
33	I can touch plants, walk near trees, or work in a garden.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Programming		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
34	There are enough spaces in this facility for <u>rehabilitation</u> programs.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
35	There are enough spaces in this facility for <u>education</u> programs.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
36	There are enough spaces in this facility for <u>religious</u> services.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
37	The design of these spaces is appropriate and helps support the activities within them.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Security Technology		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
38	The technology used in this facility, such as security cameras, helps me feel safe at work.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
39	The technology used in this facility, such as cameras, makes me feel like I'm losing privacy.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
40	The amount of technology used in this prison increases my sense of privacy at work.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Visitation		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
41	The spaces for visitation in this prison feel friendly.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
42	Tables are spaced in a way to allow for private conversations.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
43	There are appropriate spaces or activities provided to help residents interact with their kids.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

44. Improvements

If improvements could be made to your physical work environment, what three to five elements would be the **most** important to you to change?

Part II: The Assessment of Place – On-Site Researcher Evaluation

Objective Prison Data		Answers
Year of Prison / Housing Unit		
1	What year was this prison and / or housing unit constructed?	_____
Prison Layout		
2	What is the overall layout of the prison design? (Ex: Radial, campus style, courtyard, telephone pole, rectangular, etc.)	_____
3	What is the layout of the housing unit? Such as stacked tiers, open dorm, podular design, etc.	_____
Size / Type of Cell		
4	What is the average size of cells (sq feet/meters)	_____
5	What is the total number of incarcerated people in: Single cells: _____ Double cells: _____	Triple Cells: _____ Dorms: _____
6	If there are windows within living spaces, are they obscured in some way? (Ex: are they painted over, too high to see out, or have bars over them?)	_____
Size of Prison Population		
7	What is the overall prison population size?	_____
8	What is the rate of overcrowding at this institution, and specifically, in this housing unit? (Prison population / building capacity)	Institution: _____ Housing Unit: _____
Reachability		
9	How far is this facility from populated areas?	_____
10	Are there public transit options for visitors to travel to this prison?	_____
11	Does the facility offer video visitation?	_____